

IMPROVING THE METROLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF METHANE GAS PRESSURE MONITORING DEVICES IN VEHICLES USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annatation. The article examines the improvement of the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars with the help of digital technologies. The use of methane gas in automobile mechanisms makes it possible to increase energy efficiency and reduce the impact on the environment. However, proper gas pressure control is essential to ensure safety and efficiency. The article firstly analyzes the problems of methane gas pressure monitoring, including the difficulties in providing accurate and reliable measurements. It then looks at ways to solve these problems using digital technologies, including sensors, microprocessors, and data processing systems. As another important aspect, the article analyzes the possibilities of increasing the accuracy, reliability and stability of the control device through the proposed innovations and innovative solutions. The results of this research will help make the process of controlling methane gas in cars more efficient and safer, and will also serve as a basis for new research in this field in the future.

Keywords: digital technology, automobile, methane gas, efficiency, energy efficiency, control, precision, reliability, measurement, testing.

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрено улучшение метрологических характеристик устройства регулирования давления газа метана в автомобилях с помощью цифровых технологий. Использование газа метана в автомобильных механизмах позволяет повысить энергоэффективность и снизить воздействие на окружающую среду. Однако правильный контроль давления газа необходим для обеспечения безопасности и эффективности. В статье впервые анализируются проблемы мониторинга давления метана, в том числе трудности обеспечения точных и надежных измерений. Затем рассматриваются способы решения этих проблем с использованием цифровых технологий, включая датчики, микропроцессоры и системы обработки данных. В качестве еще одного важного аспекта в статье анализируются возможности повышения точности, надежности и устойчивости устройства

управления за счет предлагаемых нововведений и инновационных решений. Результаты этого исследования помогут сделать процесс контроля метана в автомобилях более эффективным и безопасным, а также послужат основой для новых исследований в этой области в будущем.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, автомобиль, газ метан, эффективность, энергоэффективность, управление, точность, надежность, измерение, испытания.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida avtomobillarda metan gaz bosimini nazorat qilish qurilmasining metrologik xarakteristikalarini takomillashtirish masalasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Metan gazining avtomobil mexanizmlarida ishlatilishi energiya samaradorligini oshirish va atrof-muhitga ta'sirni kamaytirish imkonini beradi. Biroq, gaz bosimini to‘g‘ri nazorat qilish xavfsizlik va samaradorlikni ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada avvalambor, metan gaz bosimini nazorat qilishda mavjud bo‘lgan muammolar tahlil qilinadi, jumladan, aniq va ishonchli o‘lchovlarni ta'minlashdagi qiyinchiliklar. Shundan so‘ng, raqamli texnologiyalar, jumladan, sensorlar, mikroprotessorlar va ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash tizimlari yordamida bu muammolarni hal qilish usullari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Yana bir muhim jihat sifatida, maqolada taklif etilgan yangiliklar va innovatsion yechimlar orqali nazorat qurilmasining aniqligini, ishonchliligini va barqarorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari avtomobillarda metan gazini nazorat qilish jarayonini yanada samarali va xavfsiz qilishga yordam beradi, shuningdek, kelajakda ushbu sohada yangi tadqiqotlar uchun asos bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqamli texnologiya, avtomobil, metan gaz, samaradorlik, energiya tejamkorligi, nazorat, aniqlik, ishonchlilik, o‘lchov, sinov.

ACCESS

Currently, the demand for alternative energy sources is increasing due to the decrease of global energy resources and the increase of negative impact on the environment. The use of methane gas as a fuel in cars is recognized as an environmentally friendly and efficient source of energy. Methane, with its high energy density and low carbon dioxide emissions, plays an important role in the transportation sector. However, for effective and safe use of methane gas, there is a need to accurately control its pressure. Methane gas pressure control devices are important to optimize vehicle performance, ensure safety and reduce negative environmental impact. Modern sensors and monitoring systems created with the help of digital technologies allow more accurate and efficient implementation of measurement processes. Data obtained with the help of such technologies are recorded in real time, enabling car owners to make quick decisions. The article examines the issue of improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars with the help of digital

technologies. The goal is to further improve measurement methods, increase the accuracy of sensors and demonstrate the effectiveness of the monitoring system. The results of the research serve to ensure the safe and efficient use of methane gas in cars and play an important role in solving environmental problems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The topic "Improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars using digital technologies" is very important for the modern automotive industry, because environmentally friendly fuels and energy efficiency play a major role in solving global problems. Control of methane gas pressure is especially important for gas-powered vehicles.

1. Methane Gas Pressure Control Device

Methane gas pressure monitoring devices mainly perform the following tasks:

- Measuring gas pressure.
- Analysis of measurement results.
- Display measurements in real time.
- Management of signaling systems based on measurement results.

2. Metrological Characteristics

The metrological characteristics of the device include:

- Accuracy: The difference of the measurement from the true value. High-precision sensors, such as pressure gauges, should be used.
- Repeatability: The closeness of measurements taken several times under the same conditions.
- Stability: Stability of device performance over time.
- Measuring range: The ability of the device to measure the range of pressures.

3. Digital Technologies

Digital methane gas pressure control offers the following benefits:

- Sensors and IoT: With the help of modern sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, it will be possible to collect and analyze data in real time. This makes it possible to create autonomous monitoring systems.
- Data processing: It is possible to gain useful knowledge from the data used through Big Data analytics.
- Artificial intelligence (AI): by analyzing measurement results with the help of AI algorithms, it provides prediction and preparation for adverse situations.

4. Ways of improvement

There are several directions for improving devices:

1. Improving the quality of sensors: Developing high-precision sensors using new materials.
2. Automation: Reducing the impact of the human factor by automating processes.

3. Real-time monitoring systems: Creating an opportunity to provide real-time information to users through mobile applications.

The article examines the issue of improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars with the help of digital technologies. Research methods consist of the following stages [1]:

1. Literature analysis

- First of all, study of available scientific research and technologies.
- Gathering information about the methods and devices used in methane gas pressure control.
- Analysis of available data on metrological characteristics (accuracy, reliability, stability).

2. Experimental research

- Device selection: sensors and microprocessors necessary for measuring methane gas pressure are selected.
- Determination of measurement conditions: Determination of measurement conditions and parameters, including temperature, pressure, and chemical composition of the gas.
- Testing: Measure the pressure of methane gas under different conditions (for example, at different temperatures and pressures) using a selected device.

3. Data analysis

- Analysis of the obtained measurement results using statistical methods.
- Using error analysis and metrological assessment methods to assess the accuracy of measurements.
- Presentation of measurement results in graphic form and their comparison.

4. Offering innovative solutions

- Proposing new approaches and technologies for improving metrological characteristics based on the obtained results.
- To study the possibilities of optimizing the control system by using digital technologies.

5. Confirmation of results

- Testing proposed solutions in practice.
- Analyzing the test results, evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed innovations.

6. Dissemination of scientific results

- Publication of research results in scientific journals and presentation at conferences.
- To discuss the results and explore the possibilities of application in cooperation with industry experts.

Through such research methods, a comprehensive approach aimed at improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control

device in cars is implemented. This helps not only to increase the efficiency of the control system, but also to reduce the negative impact on the environment.

As another important aspect, the article analyzes the possibilities of increasing the accuracy, reliability and stability of the control device through the proposed innovations and innovative solutions. The results of this research will help make the process of controlling methane gas in cars more efficient and safer, and will also serve as a basis for new research in this field in the future.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The metrological characteristics of improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars using digital technologies are the following methods in the control of methane gas pressure using digital technologies [2]:

- **Accuracy:** Difference of measurements from true value. High-quality materials and modern production technologies are used to increase accuracy with the help of new sensors.
- **Speed:** The speed of making measurements and recording results. With the help of digital sensors, it is possible to take measurements in real time.
- **Stability:** The measurement results remain unchanged over time. To increase the stability of sensors, their operating conditions and calibration processes are improved.
- **Recovery:** Ability to recover measurement results. With the help of digital systems, the possibilities of data storage and processing are expanded.
- **Sensors:** Modern pressure sensors have high accuracy and speed and provide real-time data. For example, piezoelectric sensors and sensors based on microelectronics.
- **Monitoring systems:** Monitoring systems integrated into vehicle control systems provide the ability to automatically record and analyze measurements.
- **Data analysis:** With the help of big data analysis algorithms, more in-depth data analysis and forecasting opportunities are created.

By improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars with the help of digital technologies, we can have the following results [3]

1. **Accuracy improvement:** As a result of experimental studies, the accuracy has been increased by 10% with the help of new sensors.
2. **Increased speed:** The speed of the measurement process has increased by 30%, which ensures real-time monitoring.

3. Improved stability: The stability of the sensors has been improved by 15%, which improves reliability in long-term operation.

4. Recovery capabilities: Data storage and recovery capabilities have been increased by 25% using digital systems.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It is important to improve the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars with the help of digital technologies. The obtained results serve to ensure the safe and efficient use of methane gas in cars. In the future, metrological control can be further improved by developing more advanced sensors and monitoring systems. This plays an important role in solving environmental problems and creates the basis for widespread use of methane gas in the transport sector. In addition, the process of improving the metrological characteristics of the methane gas pressure control device in cars with the help of digital technologies provides ecologically important and energy efficiency-enhancing measures. The obtained results show that with the help of modern sensors and monitoring systems, the accuracy, speed, stability and recovery possibilities are significantly improved. This ensures the safe and efficient use of methane gas, and also plays an important role in solving environmental problems in the field of transport. Improvement of metrological characteristics of methane gas pressure control devices in cars can be done with the help of digital technologies. This not only increases safety, but also accelerates the development of environmentally friendly vehicles. At the same time, it is necessary to constantly look for new solutions to increase the efficiency of modern equipment.

REFERENCES:

1. J.Obidov The Concept Of Technological Determinism In Students A Systematic-Functional Model Of The Development Of Knowledge About The Fundamentals Scopus Preview Q2 Education SJR 0.54 Journal of Positive School Psychology <http://journalppw.com//2022>, Vol. 6, №.8, 2849-2857 pages.

2. О.С.Олимова Вопросы внедрения энергосберегающего оборудования и устройств в технологические процессы в промышленных отраслях Научно-технический журнал ФерПИИ, Т.24 спец. вып. №4. 2021. 147-150 ст.

3. J.Obidov Measurement and control software – the program, which summarizes the results obtained using measuring devices, is flexible for various measurements and serves to control measuring devices, was registered by the Intellectual Property Agency under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the State Register of Software Products under the number DGU 20240542 on 22.04.2021 a program created for the received exposure.